

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TREATMENT OF A GENERALIZED FORM OF PATHOLOGICAL ERASURE OF HARD DENTAL TISSUES

M. Aliyev,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry Assistant

D. İsmaylov,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry

T. Aliyev

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
Department of Pediatric Dentistry
Azerbaijan Medical University

Baku, Azerbaijan

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Abstract

The article describes the use of intradental locks as additional elements for fixing a cover prosthesis in the treatment of generalized pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues.

Keywords: cover prosthesis, fixation elements, pathological erasure of hard tissues of the teeth, defects in the dentition.

The effectiveness of restoring the lost aesthetic and functional abilities of the dentoalveolar system with the help of integumentary prostheses has been proven by many authors [1,2]. In this case, a separate group is made up of clinical cases when the use of overdentures is associated with pathological abrasion of hard tissues of the teeth, especially with complicated discontinuity of the dentition and dentoalveolar deformities of various degrees. Therefore, the possibility of ensuring high-quality fixation of such structures, and, accordingly, their long-term full-fledged operation, is quite relevant.

Purpose: to improve the quality of fixation of overdentures in the treatment of generalized forms of pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues.

Orthopedic treatment of pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues is determined by the clinical state of oral tissues and in each case depends on morphofunctional changes that characterize the severity of the pathological process.

Planning for the manufacture of a removable cover prosthesis is carried out in several stages, based on the generally accepted clinical and radiological examination of patients [3,4,5]. In this aspect, the main parameters are taken into account: the strategic importance of the tooth, the value of the load on the tooth (its root), the situation of oral hygiene, the amount of treatment required to save the tooth or teeth [6]. thickness, mucosal compliance, attachment of frenulums, muscles, etc. Observance of fundamental approaches to treatment facilitates the planning of clinical and technological stages of manufacturing a cover removable denture. In generalized forms of pathological abrasion of hard tissues of the teeth with preserved continuity of the dentition after preliminary endodontic treatment, in which there are no specific features, the tissues of the teeth are prepared so that the remaining root canals are prepared

under the standard dimensions of a metal pin cast together with the original wax patrice. An important point is to ensure the maximum parallelism of the retention elements (intradental attachments of their own design) to each other. After the wax reproduction of the lock fastening is transferred into a solid cast, it is adjusted and fixed on the abutment teeth.

The interalveolar height is determined using wax templates using the anatomical and physiological method. At the stage of checking the design of the prosthesis, we pay special attention to the restoration of facial signs of normal bite height, the usefulness of occlusal relationships. Correction and imposition of a prosthesis, when modeling retention structural elements, deserves a somewhat detailed consideration. As a matrix of intradental locks, we use self-hardening hard-elastic plastic of cold polymerization.

The decisive moment in ensuring high-quality fixation of prostheses is to achieve a strong connection between the lining and the acrylic base of the prosthesis. In the clinic, the finished orthopedic structure is checked along the borders of the base and by bite. The depression for matrices previously created in the base of the cover prosthesis (the depth is determined by the vertical size of the attachment male) is thoroughly cleaned and dried. A thin layer of primer is applied to their surface for a period of 1 min. (until the solvent evaporates). When applying the primer, it is necessary to cover the entire surface,

especially carefully apply the primer to the edges. After this cavity

2/3 filled with plastic. The mixture is distributed over

prepared surface of the prosthesis and injected into the oral cavity. The patient should close his mouth and perform light chewing and swallowing movements for 6 minutes, but without much difficulty. After that, the

prosthesis is carefully removed from the oral cavity, excess mass is removed. The complexity and duration of individual orthopedic manipulations are compensated by a fairly quick final result of orthopedic treatment. Drawing up a treatment plan for generalized hard abrasion

tooth tissues, complicated by the presence of defects in the dentition, requires the selection of the optimal number of supporting teeth, taking into account the type of fixing elements. This allows for reliable cosmetic and functional effects of prosthetics.

In general, the clinical stages do not fundamentally differ from the well-known stages of the manufacture of removable dentures. Criteria for the assessment of supporting teeth are attached to the criteria for the state of the edentulous alveolar process, mucosal compliance. Particular attention should be paid to the parallelism of the fixing elements and the boundaries of the base of the prosthesis, the construction of which occurs on the basis of the creation of a closing valve along the line of the transitional fold. A feature of the design modeling will also be that in the area of missing teeth, the basis of the prosthesis must correspond to the subordinate tissues of the prosthetic bed. A separate group is made up of clinical cases when pathological erosion of hard dental tissues is complicated by discontinuity of the dentition and dentoalveolar deformities of various degrees. Difficulties in orthopedic rehabilitation of this category of patients are due to combined morphological and functional disorders that affected the occlusal relationships of the dentition, vacant alveolar process hypertrophy, blocking of the horizontal movements of the lower jaw, pain in the muscles, dysfunctional disorders of the temporomandibular joints, aesthetic disproportions.

The clinical and laboratory stages of manufacturing removable overdentures are somewhat different. The clinical situation in such patients requires preliminary separation of the occlusion with the help of plastic caps, restructuring of the chewing system reflexes and subsequent rational prosthetics with removable overdentures. The decisive advantage of the proposed method is a significant reduction in the time of orthopedic treatment, which is achieved by avoiding, if possible, the preparatory period. After all, methods of two-stage rehabilitation of patients with pathological abrasion of teeth are known, which require a long time and significant efforts of the doctor and patient to rebuild the masticatory apparatus and a full-fledged clinical effect. In this case, the use of intradental attachments, telescopic crowns, support-retaining clasps, etc. is considered optimal as additional elements of fixation. A generalized description of these stages is as follows:

- preliminary endodontic preparation of abutment teeth with their subsequent preparation;
- removal of full anatomical prints from both jaws;
- determination of the height of the central ratio of the jaws;
- modeling of wax constructions of attachments in the laboratory;
- fixation of the cast males on the abutment teeth;
- removal of functional prints;
- determination of the central ratio of the jaws (using wax bite rollers);
- checking the wax structure of the cover prosthesis;
- fabrication of matrix elements from rigid-elastic cold polymerization plastic and imposition of a finished orthopedic structure

Possible specific changes in the phasing and depending on the clinical conditions in each case should be indicated.

Therefore, the data obtained in the course of the work allow us to assert that the proposed design is quite effective in the rehabilitation of patients with generalized forms of pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues. The use of a cover prosthesis in such clinical situations provides a high degree of restoration of aesthetic and functional norms, which significantly reduces the time of orthopedic treatment. The removable nature of the design makes it possible to effectively correct the prosthesis in the process of restructuring the chewing system reflexes, based on clinical and laboratory data.

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